

Microwave thermogravimetry as a tool to evaluate the drying of refractory castables – The effects of volumetric heating

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ABSTRACT

Refractory castables present special features that render them unique and the most appropriate solution for lining specific high-temperature industrial equipment. Hydraulic bonded monolithics develop mechanical strength at room temperatures due to the hydration of some of its constituents, such as calcium aluminate cement. Their most significant drawback is the drying step, which takes place before firing and requires several hours of slow heating rates and plateaus to reduce the likelihood of facing explosive spalling. This phenomenon is a result of water vapor pressurization, as well as thermomechanical stresses. As an alternative to reduce the time and CO₂ generation, microwave heating can be a promising solution as the volumetric nature of the temperature increase can make this process safer. Besides this benefit, the likelihood of using green energy and the higher efficiency of this method add to the potential benefits. The present work analyses the mass loss of refractory castables by proposing a microwave thermogravimetry equipment. The results suggest that water removal occurs at earlier temperatures and, in total, nine-fold less energy consumption estimation. Numerical model results showed the distinct thermal gradients and the resulting

drying profiles, highlighting the importance of properly controlling the microwave power during drying. Thus, these findings indicate that the microwave process might be a valid strategy for a safer, greener and faster drying of castable refractories.

1 INTRODUCTION

Refractory castables are a versatile alternative to pre-shaped ones, as their composition can be readily adjusted and several placing techniques can be used [1]. This leads to an easier installation that can be even automatized [1,2]. After curing, hydraulic bonded castables require a careful stage of water removal [2] as for this class of materials water is added to obtain the required rheological features. This drying process requires great attention because the combination of water pressure and thermomechanical stresses can lead to cracks or even a phenomenon known as “explosive spalling” [3].

The industrial practice usually applies long heating curves as the primary countermeasure to avoid this failure mechanism [4]. The heating protocols are based on semi-empirical laws that yield high energy consumption, great carbon dioxide emissions and lengthy production halts. To address this challenge, numerical models of this process were recently developed to help the design of the heating-up curves [5,6]. Another approach is based on the understanding and development of permeability enhancing additives that can speed-up the water withdrawn from the material, such as polymeric fibers [7]. The likelihood of *in-situ* observations of the drying process via neutron tomography has been also applied to further improve its understanding such as checking the moisture clog effect carried out by Moreira et al. [8]

As the temperature increase is the main driving force and control variable during the drying process [3], the search for alternative heating methods can also lead to important advances as suggested by the technical report on microwave drying by Taira et al. [9], from Nippon Steel and by its numerical results presented by Gong et al. [10]. The present work aims to complement these studies using a newly developed microwave thermogravimetry analysis (MW-TGA), which will be compared under controlled conditions to conventional electric heated thermogravimetry, both experimentally and numerically. Therefore, the effect of the volumetric heating was isolated from other variables and a thorough understanding of the differences between these methods and the potential of microwave drying is proposed via energy consumption calculation.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Microwave Thermogravimetry Equipment

The conventional thermogravimetry equipment comprises the mass evolution measurement of the sample during a thermal treatment, often carried out in an electric resistance furnace due to its cost effectiveness and reproducibility [4]. In the current work, the same principle was reproduced within a microwave oven, resulting in the MW-TGA equipment.

Both thermal radiation and microwaves are electromagnetic sources whose wavelengths (and consequentially their frequency) lie within well specified ranges (between $0.1\mu\text{m}$ and $100\mu\text{m}$ for thermal radiation and from $100\mu\text{m}$ to 100cm for microwaves). Thus, both share the same features and follow the same physical laws when propagating through space or interacting with solid materials

[11]. The main difference between them is the fact that the microwave photons display lower frequencies, and consequently higher penetration thickness when compared to thermal radiation [12]. Thus, the thermal radiation from conventional heating only interacts with a thin layer of the material, leading to a surface increase of temperature whereas microwave heating is known to be a volumetric process [12].

Another important aspect is that different elements and molecules with distinct dielectric properties will behave differently when interacting with microwaves, such as metals that can reflect them or even a high absorption in the case of silicon carbide [13] or liquid water [12]. This feature can be beneficial for the drying of partially saturated porous medium, such as refractory castables because the regions that concentrate the water content will be selectively heated [12].

Thus, to investigate the potentials of microwave drying, the MW-TGA comprises a scale placed under the microwave oven, an alumina tube used to sustain the sample and a thermocouple, where the latter controls the power provided to the microwave's magnetron, as seen in Figure 1. As the surrounding air is not heated during the test because it is transparent to microwaves, one cannot define a "furnace temperature" for the MW-TGA, conversely to the conventional equipment. Consequently, the heating schedule is directly followed by the sample.

Using a thermocouple poses several challenges such as its location that should be in contact with the sample but not affecting the mass measurements. Additionally, the thermocouple can interact with the microwaves, reflecting them

or even acting as an antenna, or generating sparks, and under specific conditions, sustaining plasma [14]. To avoid such issues, the thermocouple was shielded and grounded, and a rubber piece was positioned between the top of the microwave cavity and the thermocouple to avoid sparks among them. The data was then collected by two independent computers (one for the temperature readings and the other for the mass values).

Because of the duration of the tests, the magnetron and the sample heating could trigger the thermal protection system of the oven and halt the tests. To prevent this, auxiliary fans were installed in the equipment. The sample holder consisted of a porous alumina scaffold and a sintered alumina tube that was placed on the top of the scale. This configuration limited the heat flux from the sample towards the scale.

Figure 1: Setup of the microwave TGA equipment - a) photograph of the system, b) schematics of its main components and c) detail of the cavity and a sample inside it.

The composition selected for comparing conventional and microwave based TGA was a high alumina castable containing 5 wt.% of calcium aluminate cement and 4.5 wt% of water, herein referred to as 5CAC (Table 1). The particle size distribution was based on Andreasen's model with a coefficient $q = 0.21$, and the preparation steps were the same as the ones reported by Cunha et al. [6]. The samples were cast in cylindrical molds with a diameter of 50mm, height of 40mm and a hole with 6mm of diameter, 20mm deep, which was drilled at the center of the sample to insert the thermocouples.

Table 1: 5CAC High-alumina refractory castable composition.

Raw Materials		Composition (wt.%)
Tabular Alumina (D<6mm)	Almatis	74
Calcined and reactive alumina	CL370, Almatis	11

	CT3000SG, Almatics	10
Calcium Aluminate Cement	Secar 71, Imerys, France	5
Dispersant	Castament FS60, BASF	0.2
Distilled Water		4.5

Following casting, the samples were cured for 24h in closed plastic bags with a beaker full of distilled water. After this step, the samples were stored and tested in the conventional or microwave TGA equipment. Both experiments followed the same protocol with a heating rate of 5°C/min from room temperature up to 625°C, with a dwell time of 20 minutes at the latter temperature. The results were analyzed following Luz et al. [4], where the weight change was normalized by the initial values and the derivative of the mass loss with respect to the temperature of the sample was calculated by a finite difference method.

2.2 Numerical Simulations

To complement the experimental results, a single-phase numerical model originally developed by Bažant et al. [15] and further adapted for microwave heating by Gong et al. [10] was implemented within the FEniCS framework. It should be noted that the current model only considers the mass and enthalpy balance and that there are more complete descriptions of the microwave heating of partially saturated porous media such as the works by Bažant and Makul [16,17], which were not adopted in the current work due to the lack of the required properties for the electromagnetic modelling of the interaction of the microwaves and the refractory castable.

Nonetheless, the present implementation can be used to qualitatively compare the differences between conventional and volumetric heating and with proper calibration of the properties, even more accurate results can be obtained.

The mass and enthalpy balance are given by Equations 1 and 2

$$\frac{\partial \rho_{ev}}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\kappa}{g} \nabla P_v \right) + \frac{\partial \rho_{deh}}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

where, ρ_{ev} is the mass of evaporable water per kilogram of castable, t the time, κ the intrinsic permeability, g the gravity acceleration (9.81 m/s²), ρ_{deh} the mass of dehydration water and P_v is the pressure inside the pores, the primary variable of the model.

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \rho C_p = \nabla \cdot (\lambda \nabla T) - C_l \frac{\kappa}{g} \nabla P_v \cdot \nabla T + \Delta H_{ev} \frac{\partial \rho_{ev}}{\partial t} + \Delta H_{deh} \frac{\partial \rho_{deh}}{\partial t} + Q_{MW} \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the density of the refractory castable, C_p its specific heat, λ the thermal conductivity, C_l the specific heat of liquid water, ΔH_{ev} and ΔH_{deh} the enthalpies of evaporation and dehydration, respectively, and T the temperature, the primary variable. Q_{MW} is the volumetric heating term that it is ignored when considering the conventional TGA case and it is given by Equation 3 for the microwave one.

$$Q_{MW} = P (A_w \rho_{ev} + A_c \rho) \quad (3)$$

where, A_w and A_c represent the microwave absorption of water and castable respectively, and following Gong et al. [10], their values were assumed to be equal to 1040 J/(Kg s) and 13 J/(Kg s). One modification of Gong's implementation is the term P which represents the power percentage of the microwave defined by a PID controller to ensure that the heating protocol is followed. The thermal boundary conditions for each case are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Thermal boundary conditions of the a) conventional and b) microwave thermogravimetry tests. All surfaces in both cases are free to exchange the mass with $q_m = h_m (P - P_\infty)$, where h_m is the mass transfer coefficient, h_T is the heat transfer coefficient, σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant, ε is the castable's emissivity, and P_∞ and T_∞ are the pressure and temperature at the ambient, respectively.

For further details on the implementation of the model, the properties used to simulate the 5CAC composition and its numerical solution, the reader is referred to Cunha et al. [6].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microwave Thermogravimetry

For conventional TGA heating, the thermal gradient within the sample can be indirectly assessed by the difference between the sample temperature and the furnace one. For the MW TGA, this measure is not representative as the air

surrounding the sample does not absorb the microwaves and, therefore, does not have its temperature increased. This however does not imply that the MW TGA sample displays a null thermal gradient. In fact, it is expected that the surfaces of the sample will be colder due to the heat exchange with the cooler surroundings. Figure 3 shows the difference of temperature between the furnace and the sample for the conventional case whereas for the MW TGA one, the plot presents the scheduled temperature instead of the furnace values, highlighting the reproducibility of the heat-up protocol by the MW TGA equipment. This was also noticeable by the observed glowing light from the thermocouple hole whereas the other surfaces of the sample were colder during the MW TGA test.

Figure 3: Furnace temperature (set program temperature for the microwave TGA) and sample temperature profile when submitted to a heating rate of 5°C/min. The dotted line represents the expected sample temperature based on the furnace one.

The mass loss is presented in Figure 4 (a) where the general behavior for the three drying stages (the evaporation, ebullition and dehydration) is similar for the two different heating methods, resulting in a total mass loss of 4.2 wt.%.

Figure 4: (a) Mass loss for the conventional and Microwave TGA, (b) derivative of mass loss with respect to the sample's temperature.

The derivative of the mass loss with respect to the sample temperature is presented in Figure 4 (b), and it highlights that the first peak of mass release occurs between 140°C and 160°C for the MW TGA samples, and 170°C for the conventional TGA. Moreover, the peaks for the microwave heated samples are roughly 15% higher than for the conventional TGA. This change in the ebullition stage of the drying is related to the difference of the temperature gradients within the sample due to the distinct heating methods. The mass increase for the MW sample 1 at roughly 560°C (Fig. 4a) and its respective derivative (Fig. 4b) can be explained by small displacements of the bottom of the sample holder that can touch the microwave cavity for brief moments. The next section presents the numerical simulations to better visualize these changes of the temperature and pressure distribution within the samples.

3.2 Numerical Simulations

Figure 5 (a) shows the comparative results of the computational model for the different TGA methods considering the temperature applied as the boundary condition (the furnace temperature for the conventional case) and the values at the center of the sample. It can be seen that the numerical model qualitatively matches the experimental behavior described in Figure 3 (a), with an initial difference for the conventional furnace and the sample temperature which is reduced when the furnace reaches above 300°C, and the characteristic oscillation for the microwave data around 200°C related to the free water removal.

Figure 5: (a) Furnace temperature (program temperature for the microwave TGA) and the sample temperature profile predicted when heated at 5°C/min and (b) modelled pressure evolution at the center of the sample.

The pressure estimations at the center of the sample for both cases are described in Figure 5 (b). The first peak related to the ebullition stage of the drying process is 11% higher for the MW TGA. This is associated to the volumetric

heating as a result of the heating rate ($5^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$) at the center of the sample observed in Figure 6 (b). This uniform heating also leads to a clearer split among the water removal mechanisms, as seen in the $200\text{-}350^{\circ}\text{C}$ range for the MW-TGA pressure profile. It can also be observed that the conventional TGA sample reproduces the same shoulder for the first and highest pressurization peak around 200°C as detected for the derivative of the mass loss presented in Figure 3 (b).

Finally, another specific observation for the MW TGA is the effect of the PID temperature oscillations between 200°C and 350°C on the pressure peaks. This can actually be an interesting feature of this drying method as this fine-tuning capability of the temperature enables the possibility of detecting cooling regimes during the heating protocol. This cannot be reproduced by the conventional heating because even if the heater is completely shut down, the unidirectional nature of this method would lead to a heat front that would still be propagating through the material, as it can also be seen when imposing long plateaus on the drying curves [7].

Figure 6 presents the thermal and pressurization state at the moment of maximum pressure observed for the MW TGA case (after 28min and 40s) for both conventional and microwave heating. Comparing the temperature distribution in Figures 6 (a) and (b) clearly highlights the distinct features of these methods.

The heating at the surface of the conventional case leads to a negative thermal gradient with the coolest positions at the center of the sample, whereas the volumetric nature of microwaves provides a smaller positive gradient due to

the lower surface temperature of the sample by the convection of the colder air in the surroundings.

The pressure distribution is a direct consequence of these distinct thermal states. The conventional TGA clearly shows two drying fronts: one from the surfaces merging at the center of the sample, and the other on the opposite direction. For the MW TGA, there is only a single front moving from the center towards the surface. The higher values of pressure for the MW TGA case also highlights the need for better control of the microwave drying step as the volumetric heating matches more closely to the heating rates imposed, which can lead to thermal stresses if such values are too high. This requirement of finer control relies on the accurate simulation of this process to properly define the power of the microwave generator at each moment of the drying process.

Figure 6: Temperature and pressure distribution at 28 minutes and 40 seconds of the test for conventional TGA, (a) and (c) and for microwave TGA (b) and (d), respectively.

3.3 Energy consumption

To compare the energy efficiency of the different heating methods, the current section presents an estimation of the energy consumed by each method during the drying of the castables. The computation is based on the energy balance of the furnace considering the energy absorbed by the sample, the air and the refractory (in the case of conventional heating), as summarized in Figure 7.

7.

Figure 7: Estimation of energy consumption of a) electric heating and b) microwave TGA equipment. The refractory lining assumed for the electric furnace

was a high alumina plate with density of 2660kg/m^3 and a specific heat of $890\text{ J}/(\text{kg K})$ from Santos et al.[18].

The microwave equipment does not have refractory walls as the main property required is to be an electromagnetic wave reflector (metallic shell). Given the fact that the sample is supported by an alumina holder, no other refractories are used. Thus, only a negligible amount of energy is consumed by the equipment walls. This is not the case for the electric furnace used in the conventional TGA equipment, where thick refractories are used next to the resistances. This leads to roughly 9 times higher total energy consumption for the conventional drying. The carbon dioxide emission for each test can be estimated by the EPA Greenhouse equivalence calculator [19], which indicates that for the conventional case 0.128 kg of CO_2 is released whereas only 0.014 kg for MW TGA during the test.

This potential for reduced environmental impacts of microwave-based drying is also valuable as microwave generators can be directly supplied from clean renewable electricity.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Due to the lower frequency, microwaves can better penetrate the refractories and provide volumetric heating, which is completely different from the thermal state resulted by conventional drying. This changes the dynamic of water removal yielding more intense mass release rate peaks at lower temperatures. Additionally, the temperature control is more precise and provides new potential strategies to energy saving and efficient drying.

The current work highlighted these specific features through thermogravimetry test analysis via a novel tool, the microwave based TGA. It was observed that the peaks related to dehydration were better defined given the volumetric heating of the samples.

Numerical simulation of these processes showed the different thermal states related to the distinct heating methods, such as the negative temperature gradient for the conventional case and the positive one for the MW TGA. The volumetric heating led to higher pressure values for this latter drying method, highlighting the importance of the proper control of the power provided by the microwave generator during the process, to prevent rapid ebullition and even thermomechanical stresses in the sample.

Finally, an estimation on the energy consumption of each test suggested that the MW TGA presented an 89% energy reduction during the drying step analyzed, resulting in lower carbon dioxide footprints for this method when compared to the conventional case.

Future works on how to properly optimize the microwave drying are still required, as well as more detailed information on the final properties of the resulting dried materials. Studies on how this potential technique scales up in a real industrial world are also crucial to assess the feasibility of this drying strategy. Nonetheless, the tool presented here can add to the understanding of this process and ultimately to the optimization of the drying of refractory castables.

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